

A New Sensitive and Selective Photometric Method of Determination of Trace Amount Molybdenum with 4-Hydroxy-Coumarinthiol

S. P. BAG, A. K. CHAKRABARTI and J. P. GOSWAMI

Chemistry Department, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 3 June 1980, revised 19 December 1980, accepted 9 June 1981

A new photometric method for the determination of molybdenum (VI) with 4-hydroxy-coumarinthiol is reported in this paper. The reagent forms a stable intensely coloured violet complex extracted in chloroform. The complex extracted from 1 M HCl absorbs maximum at 560 nm and has the molar absorptivity $1.2 \times 10^4 \text{ l. mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The system conforms to Beer's law from 0.5 to 12 ppm with optimum range 1-7 ppm at 560 nm. The Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction is $0.00812 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2} \text{ Mo(VI)}$. 7.5 times excess of Cu(II), V(V), W(VI) is tolerated and all other ions do not interfere. The stepwise and overall stability constants of the 1 : 2 complex have been determined by spectrophotometric methods.

THIO-LIGANDS¹⁻⁴ are often used for trace estimation of molybdenum as they appear to be more sensitive or selective chelating agents than others reported in the literature⁵. Several other reagents including thio-oxine and dithiol are often used for trace estimation, but the methods are not very selective in applications. Also, there are very few published papers where stepwise and overall stability constants have been reported for molybdenyl complexes with benzenethiol. A new reagent 3-mercapto-4-hydroxy-coumarin (I) has been synthesized and used as analytical reagent for spectrophotometric determination of molybdenum(VI) by solvent extraction.

The reagent is generated in situ and is found stable enough for investigation. It reacts with molybdenum(VI) to produce an intense violet coloured complex which is extracted from 0.5 M to 1.5 M HCl in chloroform. The molar absorptivity of the 1 : 2 molybdenum : thiol complex is $1.2 \times 10^4 \text{ l. mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at the absorption maximum 560 nm. The solvent extraction method described here is highly sensitive and selective. The stepwise and overall stability constants have been determined by different photometric methods and reported.

Experimental

Apparatus : A Hilger-Uvispek spectrophotometer was used for all absorbance measurements with matched 1 cm glass cells.

Reagents and solutions : Ammonium molybdate (E. Merck) was dissolved in water containing a

little ammonia and the metal was determined gravimetrically by oxine method⁶. Weaker solutions of the metal ion were prepared by dilution of the stock solution. Solutions of different ions were prepared by dissolving their salts and their strengths determined by standard methods. All chemicals were of analytical grade. E. Merck (G. R.) chloroform was directly used for extraction.

Synthesis of the reagent : The reagent was prepared by the following method⁷ : Bromine (40 ml) was added dropwise to an ice-cold solution of 4-hydroxy-coumarin (100 g) in absolute alcohol (1L) and allowed to react for half an hour. The reaction mixture was added dropwise with vigorous stirring to a mixture of ice and water (2L). The resulting slurry was kept overnight at room temperature. The crude 3-bromo-4-hydroxy-coumarin was filtered, washed with water and dried. The yield was 142 g (96%). The m.p. of the compound after recrystallization from ethylacetate was found to be 193-194°. To a solution of 3-bromo-4-hydroxy-coumarin (5 g) in absolute alcohol (50 ml) was added a solution of thiourea (1.9 g) in 50 ml of absolute alcohol. After 4 hrs of reaction at room temperature, the resulting white precipitate was filtered, washed with absolute alcohol and dried [yield 5 g (75%) ; m.p. 233-234°]. 31.7 g of the above compound was dissolved in 800 ml water under nitrogen atmosphere in a three necked flask fitted with a mechanical stirrer, dropping funnel and an inlet tube for N₂. 250 ml of 5% sodium hydroxide was added dropwise to yield a clear yellow solution. Stirring under nitrogen was continued for half an hour. 300 ml of 5% hydrochloric acid was then added dropwise. The resulting light yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with water and finally dried under *vacuo*. The recrystallized product has the m.p. 210°. (Found :

C, 50.65 ; H, 3.62 ; O, 30.83 ; S, 14.90% requires : C, 50.94 ; H, 3.77 ; O, 30.19 ; S, 15.10%). A 0.5% (w/v) aqueous solution of the reagent was always used for spectrophotometric studies.

General procedure : An appropriate amount of molybdenum(VI) solution (100 µg/ml) is taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel with 5 ml 2 M hydrochloric acid, 5 ml 0.5% reagent solution and 3 ml water giving a 15 ml volume of the aqueous phase. The coloured complex is extracted with 10 ml chloroform for 5 minutes. Extraction is repeated twice with 5 ml chloroform. The dried extract is transferred into a 25 ml standard flask and the volume made up with chloroform. The absorbance of the molybdyl complex is measured at 560 nm against solvent blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curves : The absorbance spectra show that the molybdenum complex (4 ppm) absorbs strongly between 450 nm and 700 nm and shows maximum absorbance at 560 nm. The reagent shows no absorbance against chloroform blank at the maximum. The reagent (free thiol) is highly soluble in water and other organic solvents. The complex is extracted also in iso-amyl alcohol but is found stable only for 10-15 minutes. The complex in chloroform extract was stable for more than 1 hr.

Effect of variations of acid concentrations, reagent and time : Several extractions with 4 ppm of the metal in final extract were made by varying the molar concentration of hydrochloric acid. It was found that the colour is developed in 0.1 M to 2.0 M HCl and could be extracted. The optimum acid range for the complex was found to be 0.5 to 1.5 M HCl. An acidity of 1 M HCl was maintained for all other measurements.

The colour development was also studied by varying the reagent concentration from 0.25 ml to 10 ml of 0.5% solution. The optimum range of reagent concentration needed for full colour development was found to be 4-8 ml of 0.5% reagent. 5 ml of 0.5% reagent solution was always used for all other measurements. The colour is developed immediately on the addition of the reagents and the complex is found to be stable for more than 1 hr at room temperature.

Beer's Law, optimum range and molar absorptivity : Test solutions with different concentration of molybdenum from 0.5 to 15 ppm were prepared by the recommended procedure. The system adheres to Beer's plot (1-12 ppm), shows the optimal range to be 1-7 ppm for the determination of molybdenum⁹. The relative error for this range was 2.7%. The molar absorptivity was found to be 1.2×10^4 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹; the Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction is 0.00812 µg cm⁻² of Mo(VI) at 560 nm.

Effect of diverse ions : Different amounts of interfering ions were added to a fixed amount of

molybdenum and the colour was developed according to the general procedure. At low acidity the coloured complexes formed with W(VI), V(V), Ni(II) are very unstable. The method has been found selective at higher acidity for Pt(IV), W(VI), Cu(II), V(V), Ni(II), Co(II), Pd(II) and Re(VI) ions added separately to the mixture. Anions such as oxalate, citrate, EDTA, tartarate have been tolerated within the limits shown in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF MOLYBDENUM(VI) WITH 4-HYDROXY COUMARINTHIOL ; ABSORBANCE MEASURED AT 560 nm

Ions	Added as	Tolerance Limit (ppm)	Ions	Added as	Tolerance Limit (ppm)
Ni(II)	NiCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	75	Pt(IV)	H ₂ PtCl ₆	100
Cu(II)	CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O	30	W(VI)	Na ₂ WO ₄ .2H ₂ O	30
Fe(III)	FeCl ₃ .6H ₂ O	90	V(V)	NH ₄ VO ₃	30
Co(II)	CoCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	150	NO ₂ ⁻	KNO ₃	300
Pd(II)	PdCl ₂	50	SO ₄ ²⁻	K ₂ SO ₄	300
Cr(III)	Cr ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	300	PO ₄ ³⁻	Na ₂ PO ₄	300
Zn(II)	ZnCl ₂	300	Citrate	Citric acid	300
Cd(II)	CdCl ₂	200	EDTA	Na ₂ -EDTA	300
Hg(II)	Hg(NO ₃) ₂	300	Tartarate	Tartaric acid	300
Mn(II)	MnCl ₂	300	Oxalate	Oxalic acid	300
Pb(II)	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	300	Fluoride	NaF	300
Al(III)	Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	300			

Composition of the complex : The metal : ligand composition in the molybdenum complex was determined by the method of continuous⁹ and mole ratio method¹⁰ utilizing an equimolar solutions ($1.042 \times 10^{-3} M$) of the metal and reagent. In continuous variation method, the solutions were mixed in a complementary volume of 12 ml in aqueous phase and the complex was extracted at 1 M HCl. The absorbance plotted against M/M+R shows a sharp break (at 560 nm) corresponding to a 1 : 2 metal : ligand composition in the molybdenum complex. In mole ratio method, the plot of absorbance against amount of reagent added indicates again a 1 : 2 Mo(VI) : thiol ratio in the complex at 560 nm. Equimolar solutions of molybdenum and reagent ($1.042 \times 10^{-3} M$) were utilized in the experiment.

Degree of dissociation and stability constant : The overall stability constant has been calculated following Harvey-Manning's method¹¹. The degree of dissociation α has been obtained from the relation $\alpha = A_m(.492) - A_s(.388) / A_m(.492)$ where A_m is the maximum absorbance and A_s is the absorbance corresponding to the inflexion point in mole ratio plot. The instability constant K' was obtained from the equation $K' = 4\alpha^2 C^2 / 1 - \alpha$ for a 1 : 2 complex where C ($4.169 \times 10^{-5} M$) is the actual molar concentration of the molybdyl thiolate complex. The degree of dissociation and stability constant values were found to be 0.2150 and 10.06 (log k), respectively. The stepwise stability constants were evaluated following two different photometric methods. The equilibrium ligand concentrations for the 1 : 2 (Mo : R) complex and the degree of complex formation function (ϕ) were

calculated from Beer's Law. The constructions of suitable functions and their evaluation by the graphical plots as developed earlier were also made. The stepwise stability constants were found to be 5.07 ($\log k_1$), 4.63 ($\log k_2$) based on Leden's idea on degree of complex formation (φ) and 5.20 ($\log k_1$), 4.90 ($\log k_2$) based on Yatsimirskii method applied to spectrophotometry. The K_{ov} values given by different photometric methods agreed well with each other.

References

1. E. W. HABART and E. P. HURLEY, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, **27**, 144.
2. R. J. MAGEE and A. S. WITWIT, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1963, **29**, 27.
3. H. BUSS, H. W. KOHLSCHUTTER and MIHDTANK, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1960, **178**, 1.
4. J. E. WELLS and R. PEMBERTON, *Analyst*, 1940, **65**, 152.
5. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd Edn., Interscience, New York, 1959.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd Edn., Longmans, London, 1964.
7. M. PANTLITSCHKE and H. BENGHER, *Monatsh.*, 1950, **81**, 81.
8. A. RINGBOM, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1938, **115**, 332.
9. W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.
10. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Indn. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **66**, 111.
11. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4744.